

BUNDLE REINFORCED POLYMER COMPOSITES FOR NOVEL STRUCTURAL BATTERIES

Yalin YU¹, Boming ZHANG², Guocheng QI³ and Zhanwen TANG⁴

¹School of Materials Science and Engineering, Beihang University
Room 542, New Main Building, No. 37 Xueyuan Road, Haidian District, Beijing, China
Email: yuyalin@buaa.edu.cn

² School of Materials Science and Engineering, Beihang University
Room 542, New Main Building, No. 37 Xueyuan Road, Haidian District, Beijing, China
Email:qigc@buaa.edu.cn

³ School of Materials Science and Engineering, Beihang University
Room 542, New Main Building, No. 37 Xueyuan Road, Haidian District, Beijing, China
Email: zbm@buaa.edu.cn

⁴ School of Materials Science and Engineering, Beihang University
Room 530, New Main Building, No. 37 Xueyuan Road, Haidian District, Beijing, China
Email: tangzhanwen@163.com

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ABSTRACT

In this paper, a novel structural battery was designed based on the carbon fiber bundle composites (CFBC), and the electrochemical and mechanical properties were measured experimentally and analyzed numerically.

1 INTRODUCTION

Mass reduction has become vital to the car design for the decrease of aerodynamic resistance[1]. The preliminary method is to introduce multifunctionality into composites in order to realize structural and energy storage properties simultaneously [2]. In this paper, a novel structural battery was designed based on the carbon fiber bundle composites (CFBC), and the electrochemical and mechanical properties were measured experimentally and analyzed numerically.

2 GENERAL SPECIFICATIONS

The carbon fiber bundles as electrode and the glass fiber separators were impregnated with the electrolyte copolymerized from methacrylate monomer mixtures separately. Subsequently, the glass fiber separators and the aluminum foils deposited with cathode material (LiFePO₄) wrapped up the bundles sequentially. Finally, the bundle composites were arranged and fixed in a line, and cured with epoxy resin by Resin Transfer Molding process. The sample can be seen as a single layer of “bundle reinforced polymer composites” (BRPC) (see Fig. 1), in which the carbon fiber bundle composites are considered as reinforced constituent and the epoxy resin is responsible for the load transfer.

Both the cell capacity after different electrochemical cycles and the reversible capacities at different lithiation rates of the CFBCs and BRPCs were investigated for the evaluation of the composite electrochemical properties. Good results achieved suggest a high potential for the use in battery applications. In addition, the tensile mechanical properties of this structural battery were tested and analyzed numerically in this work. The tensile strengths of both the T800H single carbon fiber (SCF) and CFBCs were found to follow the Weibull Distribution (see Table 1). Numerical models with different ratios of the minor and major axes of the cross-section of the bundles were established for the tensile mechanical evaluation, and the calculating material parameters were shown in Table 2.

With the decrease of the ratio, the calculating modulus of the BRPCs increases gradually and approaches to a constant in the case of BRPCs with $V_{\text{bundle}} = 35\%$ vol. in the composites and $V_{\text{fiber}} = 50\%$ vol. in every bundle (see Figure 2). The calculating modulus ranges from 27 GPa to 29 GPa, which suggests a great improvement of structural battery on the mechanical properties in comparison with laminate batteries and micro batteries.

3 FIGURES AND TABLES

Table 1 The Weibull distribution parameters of T800H-CFBC and T800H-SCF

	$\sigma_{\text{mean}}/\text{MPa}$	CV	m	σ_0/MPa
T800H-CFBC	5176	4.5%	26.57	5281
T800H-SCF	5147	23.3%	5.20	5592

Table 2 Material parameters of bundle reinforced polymer composites for finite element modeling.

	Thickness/mm	modulus/GPa	Poisson's ratio
T800H-FCBC	R=0.5	170	0.3
Epoxy resin	—	3.4	0.4
Aluminum foil	0.02	8	0.35
Glass fiber separator	0.5	80	0.3

Figure 1 Schematic illustration of the bundle reinforced polymer composites

Figure 2 The simulating tensile modulus in longitudinal direction in the representative volume element of bundle reinforced polymer composites: (a) the numerical model with different ratios of minor and major axes of the bundles in the cross-section, (b) boundary conditions, and (c) the relation between simulating tensile modulus and the ratio.

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A paragraph at the end of the paper (before the references) may be added (optional) for acknowledgments. It should be entitled with the word **ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS** centred, in 11 pt boldface Times New Roman.

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